

EXPLORING TOURISM AND TRANSPORTATION VOCABULARY IN ENGLISH, KOREAN AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract. In this article, I will compare some types of travel words, origin of the words, their similarities and differences in English, Korean and Uzbek languages. This article and vocabulary is intended to make tourism terminology easy to learn for both students and travellers. These vocabulary terms are essential for everyday conversations, travel planning, and navigating transportation systems in English-speaking, Korean-speaking and Uzbek-speaking regions. Whether you're taking a leisurely stroll or embarking on a cross-country journey, knowing these terms can enhance your travel experience and facilitate seamless communication.

Key words: tourism and transportation, tourism terminology, duty-free goods, guide, hitchhiking, go backpacking, truck, vacation.

Introduction

Transportation is an important aspect of daily life, connecting people and goods across cities and countries. Whether commuting to work, traveling for leisure, or transporting goods for trade, understanding transportation vocabulary in both English, Korean and Uzbek languages can facilitate effective communication and navigation in diverse settings. Especially, for those who are majoring tourism and hospitality, knowing these words are considered to be the most fundamental and crucial ones.

Main body

¹“Ship” in Korean

The most common word for “ship” in Korean is 배 (bae). However, in some cases, different words may apply. For example, a mail steamer, which is a boat carrying post and mail, is called 우편선 (upyeonseon) in Korean. Meanwhile, a cruise ship, which is the type of ship you'd use during your travels,

¹ “Korean phrasebook” by J.D.Hilts and Minkyung Kim. 3rd edition, March 2002, Lonely Planet Publications

is called 유람선 (yuramseon). And the word for “ferry” in Korean is 연락선 (yeollakseon).

“Airport” in Korean

You can say “airport” in Korean as 공항 (gonghang). Here, you’ll be able to ride an airplane which is called 비행기 (bihaenggi) in Korean.

The word for “flight” in Korean is 비행 (bihaeng). The word for “domestic flight” is 국내선 (gunnaeseon), and for “international flight,” it is 국제선 (gukjeseon).

Let's delve into some common transportation terms in English and their corresponding translations in Korean and Uzbek languages. There will be given vocabulary list for tourism and transportation below in alphabetical order.

²Vocabulary list for tourism and transportation in English, Korean and Uzbek.

English	Korean(한국어)	Uzbek(O'zbekcha)
Adventure	모험 (moheom)	sarguzasht
Airplane	비행기(bihengi)	samolyot
Airport	공항 (gonghang)	aeroport
Arrival	도착(dochak)	yetib kelish
Baggage claim	수하물 찾기 (suhamul chatki)	yuk(bagaj)ni olish
Bicycle	자전거(chajongo)	velosiped
Boarding gate	탑승 게이트 (tapseung geiteu)	bortga chiqish eshigi
Boarding pass	탑승권 (tapseunggwon)	bortga chiqish taloni
Bus	버스 (boseu)	avtobus
Boat	보트(boteu)	qayiq
Departure	출발 (chulbal)	jo'nab ketish

² Collins Korean phrasebook, Harper Collins Publishers,2007. www.collins.co.uk

Duty-free goods	면세품 (myeonsepum)	boj to'lanmaydigan mahsulot
Emergency exit	비상 출구 (bisang chulgu)	favqulodda chiqish eshigi
Entry gate	출입문 (churipmun)	kirish eshigi
Ferry	페리(peri)	parom
Foreign country	해외(haewe)	chet el
Go backpacking	배낭여행을 가다	ryukzakli sayohatga chiqish
Helicopter	헬리콥터(hellikopto)	vertolyot
Hitchhiking	히치하이킹 (hichihaiking)	hitchhiking(o'tkinchi odamlarning transportida bepul sayohat qilish)
Hotel	호텔 (hotel)	mehmonxona
Life vest	구명조끼 (gumyeongjokki)	qutqaruv nimchasi
Lost and found	분실물 보관소 (bunsilmul bogwanso)	topilmalar byurosi
Local,domestic	국내 여행(gugnae yeohaeng)	mahalliy sayohat
Luggage	짐 (jim)	yuk
Map	지도 (jido)	xarita
Motorcycle	오토바이(eoteobai)	mototsikl
Passport	여권 (yeogwon)	pasport
Plane ticket	비행기표 (bihaenggipyo)	samolyot chiptasi
Rail ticket	기차표 (gichapyo)	poezd chiptasi
Scooter	스쿠터(seokuto)	skuter
Subway	지하철 (jihacheol)	metro
Taxi	택시(taekshi)	taksi

Ticket machine	표 판매기 (pyo panmaegi)	bilet mashinasi
Tour guide	여행 가이드 (yeohaeng gaideu)	sayohat yo'lboshchisi(gid)
To pack	짐을 싸다 (jimeul ssada)	yuklarini joylamoq
To travel	여행 가다 (yeohaeng gada) or 여행을 가다	sayohat qilmoq yoki sayohatga bormoq
Train	기차(gicha)	poezd
Tram	전차(choncha)	tramvay
Travel expenses	여행 경비 (yeohaeng gyeongbi)	sayohat xarajatlari
Trip or Travel	여행(yeohaeng)	sayohat
Travel sickness	멀미 (meolmi)	sayohat kasalligi
Trip abroad	해외여행 (haeoyeohaeng)	chet elga sayohat
Truck	트럭(teorok)	katta yuk mashinasi
Vacation	휴가 (hyuga)	ta'til

Conclusion

This article aims to provide a comprehensive summary of essential vocabulary related to tourism and transportation, covering key terms and phrases that travellers and industry professionals frequently encounter. Mastering the vocabulary related to tourism and transportation is essential for travellers to navigate smoothly during their journeys and for industry professionals to effectively communicate with customers. By familiarizing themselves with these terms and phrases, individuals can enhance their travel experiences and ensure efficient tourism and transportation arrangements. As it is understandable from the article, most of the modern tourism terms in Korean language were borrowed from English language directly. Whereas, many Uzbek tourism terms, like the terms of other modern spheres, were borrowed from other languages through the Russian language. It is obvious that, there were many changes and misunderstandings in that process. Thus, Uzbek students may have difficulties in learning and understanding some words directly from

English language, which is the most global and informative language in our modern world.

In conclusion, I want our Uzbek students, no matter in Uzbekistan or abroad, who are studying tourism and hospitality, to learn these terms directly from English language. If it is needed, tourism terms should be borrowed from English or should be made using national words, like Korean.

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